

IMI2 821520 - ConcePTION

ConcePTION

WP5 – Dissemination and education for HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women and general public

D5.14 Annual report on external communications for impact assessment January 2023 - December 2023

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Document History

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Abstract

The main aim of WP5 is to improve the value, quality, and harmonisation of the dissemination of information on the available evidence related to medicines use in pregnancy and during breastfeeding.

The 5.3 sub-task aim is to engage HCPs, pregnant and breastfeeding women, and general public to stimulate pregnancy reporting through PV systems, by increasing their awareness that they can play an active role in increasing general knowledge about the safety of drug use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The objective of this report is to summarize communication actions performed in WP5 to disseminate knowledge about medicines use during pregnancy and lactation and to engage pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals (HCPs) in the ConcePTION ecosystem between January and December 2024. The communications actions may have different targets and different messages.

For this report on the fifth year of the project, the main communication activities were related to engage key stakeholders in the ConcePTION ecosystem and to stimulate reporting on medicine use during pregnancy and breastfeeding.

Methods

The objective of the report is to make an inventory of communication actions performed in WP5 on the fifth year of the project.

The communication actions are classified by their objective:

- Engagement of pregnant and breastfeeding women and healthcare professionals in the ConcePTION ecosystem
- Increase awareness and stimulate reporting on medicine use in pregnancy and breastfeeding.

The communications actions are grouped by objective and are described using the following parameters: the geographical reach, the target audience, the channel used, the date of dissemination, and the main presenter.

Results

The communication actions for this report are divided into:

- Targeted actions to engage women in the ConcePTION ecosystem with focus on breastfeeding women to participate to breast milk collection
- Targeted actions to increase awareness and stimulate reporting via different channels
- Targeted actions to prepare sustainability plan

The ConcePTION project channels include a project website (<https://www.imi-conception.eu/>), and a Twitter/X account, a YouTube channel, a LinkedIn account, and an e-mail newsletter used to drive traffic to said website by sharing links. The evolving landscape of social media algorithms has led to a reduction in the visibility, or *organic reach*, of content containing external links on various platforms. Despite these changes to the algorithms, the reach of our channels remains substantial.

On Twitter/X (<https://twitter.com/IMIconception>), we are followed by 556 users (as of 11 March 2024), with organic reach through their networks. During 2023, on average, our tweets averaged 5580+ views per month (January and February data is not available due to later retracted changes performed by Twitter/X at the time).

The project's newsletter audience is building through project events, and currently reaches 770 subscribers, representing a wide variety of stakeholders. In 2023, each newsletter issued was opened 1600+ times on average. With an average of around 650 subscribed recipients, this suggests a high level of engagement among our audience in terms of forwarding the newsletters within their own networks. As a result of this, our *organic reach* exceeded our subscriber count by 60 %.

On LinkedIn (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception/>), the project has 561 followers, with a wide organic reach, where posts average 200+ views per month. YouTube (<https://www.youtube.com/@imiconception6542>) is primarily used as a video repository, and with only 44 subscribers, we have registered close to 4 700+ views in total since the launch in February 2020.

Actions to engage women in the ConcePTION ecosystem were conducted through web communication and use of social media in various European countries and reaching international organizations. The communications actions to engage women have been conducted ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (twitter campaigns (<https://twitter.com/IMIConception>), LinkedIn campaigns (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception>), web posts (https://www.imi-conception.eu/news-details/?news_id=816), etc).

Table 1: Communication actions to engage women

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on communication tool kit launch)	February 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on ConcePTION project update)	March 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on ConcePTION update on international women day)	March 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on need of data on how medicines affect breastfeeding and the baby)	April 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on need of data on how medicines affect breastfeeding and the baby)	April 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn at world breastfeeding week on learning healthcare system)	August 2023	IHI IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on the role of solidarity to improve knowledge on medications used during pregnancy)	August 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on the role of solidarity to improve knowledge on medications used during pregnancy)	August 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on the challenge of medicine safety in breastfeeding)	October 2023	IMI ConcePTION

Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on the challenge of medicine safety in breastfeeding)	October 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on #MedSafetyWeek campaign)	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on #MedSafetyWeek campaign))	October 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on Meds4Mums2B [Meds for mums to be] app launch	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on Meds4Mums2B [Meds for mums to be] app launch	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION

The communications actions to raise awareness on the knowledge bank and to stimulate reporting have been conducted by task 5.3 members with support of ConcePTION communication task force through different channels (twitter campaigns (<https://twitter.com/IMIconception>), LinkedIn campaigns (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/imi-conception>), web posts (https://www.imi-conception.eu/news-details/?news_id=816), webinars, and face to face presentations, etc).

Table 2: Communication actions to increase awareness on knowledge bank and to stimulate reporting of exposure during pregnancy and breastfeeding

Country/Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Webinar on ConcePTION project update	February 2023	Miriam Sturkenboom and Michael Steel
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Webinar on communication tool kit launch	March 2023	Marjolein Willemsen, Anna Holm, Josepine Fernow, Agnes Kant, Sally Stephens (on behalf of task 5.3)
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on communication tool kit launch	March 2023	IMI ConcePTION

Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on main data fields needed for pregnancy pharmacovigilance)	April 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on main data fields needed for pregnancy pharmacovigilance)	April 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on the need of more data on how medicines affect breastfeeding and the baby)	April 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on the need of more data on how medicines affect breastfeeding and the baby)	April 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on quality of information for pregnancy pharmacovigilance data case reports)	July 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on quality of information for pregnancy pharmacovigilance data case reports)	July 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	ENTIS members	Face to face presentation at ENTIS annual meeting on knowledge bank	August/September2023	Benedikte Cuppers and Agnes Kant on behalf of Task 5.2, and 5.4
Global	ENTIS members	Poster presentation on communication tool kit at ENTIS annual meeting	August/September2023	Alison Oliver on behalf of Task 5.3
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on core data elements for pregnancy pharmacovigilance)	September 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on core data elements for pregnancy pharmacovigilance)	September 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on Making medicines safer for pregnant and breastfeeding women)	October 2023	IMI ConcePTION Uppsala reports
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on Making medicines safer for pregnant and breastfeeding women)	October 2023	IMI ConcePTION Uppsala reports

Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on Meds4Mums2B [Meds for mums to be] app launch	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on Meds4Mums2B [Meds for mums to be] app launch	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Web (post in ConcePTION news on #MedSafetyWeek campaign)	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on #MedSafetyWeek campaign and how to report)	November 2023	IMI ConcePTION
Global	Women, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Social media (post in LinkedIn on core data elements for pregnancy pharmacovigilance studies)	November 2023	IHI

The communications actions to raise awareness on the knowledge bank and to prepare sustainability stimulate reporting have been conducted by task 5.3 members with support of ConcePTION sustainability task force.

Table 3: Communication actions to increase awareness to prepare sustainability

Country/ Region	Target Audience (Government, General Public, Women, Pregnant Women, HCP Organizations, Industry, Pharmacists, etc.)	Channel (Social Media, Newspaper, face to face, etc.)	Date	Who Presented
Global	ENTIS members	Face to face presentation at ENTIS annual meeting	August/September 2023	Benedikte Cuppers and Agnes Kant on behalf of Task 5.2, and 5.4
Global	Government, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Face to face presentation on ConcePTION outputs at IHD annual conference on building trust in health data	November 2023	Constanza Andaur Navarro on behalf of ConcePTION
Global	Government, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Face to face presentation on knowledge bank at IHD annual conference on building trust in health data	November 2023	Miranda van Tuyl on behalf of WP5
Global	Government, health care professionals, other stakeholders	Grant request to Bill and Melinda Gates' Foundation as part of Opportunities to Advance Women's Health Innovation	December 2023	Miranda van Tuyl on behalf of WP5

Discussion and Conclusion

In the fifth year of the project, the communication efforts were focused on engaging women, raising awareness on medicines use during pregnancy and breastfeeding and stimulating reporting as well as engaging new stakeholders to increase awareness and prepare sustainability plan. On the remaining year of the project, the communication efforts will continue to focus on these three objectives before the final release of the MUMS knowledge bank.